

Examining Behavioral Intention and Use Behavior of Bukalapak in Digital Technology Adoption

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ABSTRACT: This study examines the adoption of the Bukalapak e-commerce application among users in the Tangerang Raya region, focusing on factors that shape usage intention and actual usage behavior. Despite the rapid growth of digital marketplaces, differences in user perceptions regarding system usefulness, ease of use, and social influence remain a challenge in sustaining continuous platform usage. Accordingly, this research aims to analyze how performance expectancy, effort expectancy, and social influence contribute to usage intention and how these factors, together with usage intention, are reflected in actual usage behavior. A descriptive and verificative research design was employed using a survey method. Data were collected through structured questionnaires distributed to 384 Bukalapak users in Tangerang Raya. The collected data were analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling–Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) version 4.0. The results reveal that performance expectancy, effort expectancy, and social influence simultaneously and partially have a significant effect on usage intention. Furthermore, performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and usage intention partially show a significant influence on actual usage behavior. These findings indicate that users' perceptions of system performance, ease of use, and social environment play an important role in encouraging both intention and consistent use of digital commerce platforms. The study concludes that strengthening functional performance, simplifying system interaction, and reinforcing positive social cues are essential strategies for enhancing sustainable usage behavior of e-commerce applications such as Bukalapak.

KEYWORDS: Performance Expectancy; Effort Expectancy; Social Influence; Behavioral Intention; Use Behavior

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of digital technology, particularly the internet, has brought significant changes to various aspects of people's lives, including economic activities and consumption patterns (Caniago & Putra, 2024). The internet has now become a primary need, supporting communication, access to information, learning, and online transactions without the constraints of space and time (Damayanti et al, 2023). In Indonesia, internet penetration continues to increase, with the number of users reaching 212 million, or approximately 74.6% of the total population, by 2025, with access dominated by mobile devices (Fatihanisya & Purnamasari, 2021). This situation has driven the growth of the digital economy ecosystem, particularly the e-commerce sector, which has shown significant growth in transaction value from year to year, despite occasional fluctuations. National data also shows that Java Island, including the Greater Tangerang area, is one of the centers of e-commerce business growth with a large number of business players.

Bukalapak is an online marketplace platform that facilitates easy and fast buying and selling for both sellers and buyers. The app allows sellers to open a store for free and offer a variety of everyday products, while buyers can search and transact with sellers across Indonesia, in both small and large quantities. As one of Indonesia's leading marketplaces, Bukalapak emphasizes convenience and trust through its transaction protection system, including a refund guarantee in the event of a failed delivery.

Table 1. Comparison of Top E-Commerce Brand Index in Indonesia 2020-2024

Brand	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Shopee	20,0	41,8	43,7	45,8	50,5
Lazada	31,9	15,2	15,1	15,1	13,3
Tokopedia	15,8	16,7	14,9	11,3	10,4
Bukalapak	12,9	9,5	4,7	4,7	7,6
Blibli.com	8,4	8,1	10,1	10,6	6,6

Source: www.topbrand-award.com

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Table 1 shows a comparison of the Brand Index of the five largest e-commerce platforms in Indonesia during the period 2020–2024. Shopee showed the most consistent and significant upward trend, from 20.0 in 2020 to 50.5 in 2024, thus occupying the top position throughout the observation period. In contrast, Lazada and Tokopedia tended to experience a decline in the brand index, especially after 2021. Bukalapak showed a sharp decline in the period 2020–2022, then relatively stabilized in 2023 and increased again in 2024, although still below its main competitor. Meanwhile, Blibli.com showed fluctuations with an increase in 2022–2023 before declining again in 2024. These findings illustrate the dynamics of intense competition in the Indonesian e-commerce industry with changes in consumer brand preferences over time.

The dynamics of the Brand Index indicate that the success of an e-commerce platform is determined not only by its presence in the market but also by the extent to which users actually utilize the application on a sustainable basis. In this context, Usage Behavior is a crucial aspect because it reflects actual user behavior, as reflected in the frequency and intensity of system use (Srimulyo & Pradani, 2022). Usage Behavior is a direct manifestation of behavioral intention, although in practice it can still be influenced by external factors such as the availability of supporting facilities and technical barriers. One of the main determinants of Usage Behavior is Usage Intention, which is an individual's tendency to utilize technology in daily activities (Prakarsa & Nursyanti, 2025). This intention is formed through several key factors, including Performance Expectations, Ease Expectations, and Social Encouragement (Winarno & Roostika, 2024).

Performance Expectations reflect an individual's belief that using an application can provide tangible benefits and increase the effectiveness of their activities (Wang et al., 2020). In the context of Bukalapak, these expectations relate to users' perceptions that the application can simplify transactions and provide added value compared to other platforms (Shantika et al., 2022). Furthermore, Ease of Use Expectations also plays a significant role in shaping usage intentions, as demonstrated by the perceived ease of learning, operating, and using application features without significant obstacles (Oktafani & Sisilia, 2020; Nurfitri et al., 2024). In addition to these factors, Social Influence also influences usage intentions, namely the extent to which an individual's decisions are influenced by recommendations, support, and influence from social environments such as family and friends (Mizal & Wijayanka, 2020; Maheswari & Meiranto, 2024). The combination of these three factors together shapes usage intentions, which ultimately drives continued usage behavior.

Previous research has extensively examined the relationship between performance expectancy, ease of use expectancy, and social incentives on intention to use and their implications for usage behavior, but the findings remain inconsistent. Several studies found that performance expectancy significantly influences intention to use (Caniago & Putra, 2024; Nurfitri et al., 2024; Oktafani & Sisilia, 2020; Shantika et al., 2022), while others reported insignificant results (Al-Mamary, 2022; Alkhowaiter, 2022; Aswani et al., 2018; Barbosa et al., 2022). Similar inconsistencies are also seen in ease of use expectations, where some studies have shown a significant influence on intention to use (Fatihanisya & Purnamasari, 2021; Maheswari & Meiranto, 2024; Mizal & Wijayanka, 2020), but other studies have shown no significant influence (Cao et al., 2022; Erjavec & Manfreda, 2022; Korkmaza et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2020). In addition, social encouragement in several studies has been shown to have a significant effect on intention to use (Jayaseelan et al., 2020; Khechine et al., 2020; Paramita & Cahyadi, 2024; Roh et al., 2023), but other studies state the opposite (Abdat, 2020; Abu-Taieh et al., 2022; Almagrashi et al., 2023; Patil et al., 2020). Disagreement also occurs in the relationship between intention to use and usage behavior, where some studies found a significant effect (Dhiman et al., 2020; Paramita & Cahyadi, 2024; Ramadhina et al., 2025), while other studies reported no significant effect (Dhingra & Gupta, 2020; Kasri & Yuniar, 2021; Muangmee et al., 2021; Sitthipon et al., 2022).

Based on the dynamics of e-commerce competition, the conceptual framework of technology use, and the inconsistency of previous research findings, this study aims to analyze the influence of performance expectations, ease of use expectations, and social incentives on the intention to use and their implications for the behavior of using the Bukalapak application, so that it is expected to be able to provide a more comprehensive empirical understanding in explaining the behavior of e-commerce users in Indonesia.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology model is a comprehensive theory for predicting how individuals will adopt and use a technological system (Venkatesh et al., 2003). This design model consists of a combination of several models that examine the behaviors and influences that can encourage individuals to adopt or accept a technological system. Venkatesh et al. (2003) created the UTAUT model, which has a 70% evidentiary strength.

Performance Expectancy is defined as the degree to which an individual believes that using a system or application will provide tangible benefits and enhance performance in carrying out specific activities (Venkatesh et al., 2012; Al-Mamary, 2022; Alkhowaiter, 2022). This construct is a critical determinant in digital technology adoption, as users tend to adopt applications perceived to improve efficiency, productivity, and transactional effectiveness (Wang et al., 2020; Shantika et al., 2022). In e-commerce platforms such as Bukalapak, performance expectancy is reflected in users' beliefs that the application can simplify buying and selling processes and deliver added value compared to competing platforms (Winarno & Roostika, 2024).

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Effort Expectancy refers to the extent to which an individual believes that using a system is free of effort and does not require substantial technical skills or complexity (Venkatesh et al., 2012; Oktafani & Sisilia, 2020). Key indicators of this construct include ease of learning features, clarity of the interface, and minimal technical obstacles during usage (Nurfritri et al., 2024). A positive perception of ease of use encourages greater acceptance and sustained use of digital applications, including e-commerce platforms such as Bukalapak (Winarno & Roostika, 2024).

Social Influence is defined as the degree to which an individual perceives that important others, such as family members, friends, or social groups, influence their decision to use a particular technology (Venkatesh et al., 2012; Erjavec & Manfreda, 2022). Social influence may manifest through recommendations, positive opinions, or conformity to prevailing usage trends within social environments (Roh et al., 2023). In the adoption of the Bukalapak application, social influence emerges when individuals are encouraged to use the platform based on endorsements from close social circles or widespread usage within their community (Mizal & Wijayangka, 2020).

Behavioral Intention represents the degree of an individual's willingness, commitment, and readiness to use a technology within a specific period of time (Venkatesh et al., 2012; Paramita & Cahyadi, 2024). This construct is widely recognized as the primary predictor of actual usage behavior in technology adoption models, as it reflects users' evaluations of perceived benefits, ease of use, and social influence (Maheswari & Meiranto, 2024). In this study, behavioral intention reflects users' tendency to continue utilizing the Bukalapak application as a primary digital transaction platform (Prakarsa & Nursyanti, 2025).

Use Behavior refers to actual user behavior as reflected in the frequency, duration, and intensity of system or application usage (Venkatesh et al., 2012; Srimulyo & Pradani, 2022). Use behavior represents the realization of behavioral intention, although it may also be influenced by external factors such as supporting infrastructure and technical constraints (Ramadhina et al., 2025). A high level of use behavior indicates successful technology adoption and sustained utilization of the Bukalapak e-commerce platform by its users (Prakarsa & Nursyanti, 2025).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

HYPOTHESIS

The Influence of Performance Expectancy on Behavioral Intention

Performance expectancy is defined as the degree to which an individual believes that using a system will help them attain gains in job performance or daily activities (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Individuals are more likely to adopt new technologies if they perceive them to be useful, capable of increasing productivity, and providing functional benefits (Alalwan et al., 2022). Previous research indicates that when users perceive high utility from a digital platform, their intention to use it becomes significantly stronger (Alkhowaiter, 2022). Thus, functional advantages serve as a primary determinant in shaping behavioral intention (Solihin et al., 2025).

H1: Performance Expectancy has a positive influence on Behavioral Intention

The Influence of Effort Expectancy on Behavioral Intention

Effort expectancy refers to the degree of ease associated with the use of a technology system (Venkatesh et al., 2003). If a platform is designed with an intuitive interface and requires minimal mental effort, users will be more motivated to adopt it (Bajunaied et al., 2023). Accessibility and efficient navigation have been proven to be crucial factors driving individual intention to adopt digital financial services and e-learning platforms (Azizah et al., 2024). A user's confidence in operating a system without complex technical hurdles accelerates the overall adoption process (Almagrashi et al., 2023).

H2: Effort Expectancy has a positive influence on Behavioral Intention

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The Influence of Social Influence on Behavioral Intention

Social influence reflects the extent to which an individual perceives that important others, such as family, friends, or colleagues, believe they should use the new technology (Venkatesh et al., 2003). In a highly connected digital ecosystem, influence from social circles and public opinion significantly determines an individual's decision to try a platform (Abdat, 2020). The phenomenon of herd behavior often occurs when individuals observe their social groups gaining benefits from a specific technology (Erjavec & Manfreda, 2022). Peer support and recommendations significantly enhance a person's intention to engage with technological innovations (Sarker et al., 2025).

H3: Social Influence has a positive influence on Behavioral Intention

The Influence of Performance Expectancy on Use Behavior

Performance expectancy does not stop at the intention stage; it also directly impacts how frequently and consistently an individual uses technology in real-life scenarios (Venkatesh, 2021). When a system tangibly solves user needs and delivers effective outcomes, users will integrate it into their routine behavior (Ilhamsyah & Purnamasari, 2021). The success of a technology in meeting its promised performance outcomes reinforces long-term usage behavior (Auyeung et al., 2025). Positive experiences regarding system performance drive the transition from mere trial to active and habitual use (Paramita & Cahyadi, 2024).

H4: Performance Expectancy has a positive influence on Use Behavior

The Influence of Effort Expectancy on Use Behavior

The level of ease felt when interacting with technology has a direct impact on actual usage behavior (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Systems perceived as free from technical difficulties will be used more frequently than complex ones, regardless of the magnitude of benefits offered (Ilhamsyah & Purnamasari, 2021). Operational simplicity ensures that there are no significant barriers for users to continue performing transactions or activities through the platform (Korkmaza et al., 2022). Therefore, a seamless and easy user experience directly increases the intensity of long-term technology usage (Zhoua et al., 2020).

H5: Effort Expectancy has a positive influence on Use Behavior

The Influence of Social Influence on Use Behavior

Influence from the social environment can pressure or encourage an individual to remain active in using a technology to maintain social relationships or status (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Evolving social norms often create standardized behaviors where individuals feel the need to continue using certain applications to remain relevant within their group (Fatihanisya & Purnamasari, 2021). This continuous social pressure transforms initial intention into actual and consistent usage actions (Sangeeta & Tandon, 2021). A supportive social environment creates an ecosystem where usage behavior becomes expected and commonplace (Ramadhina et al., 2025).

H6: Social Influence has a positive influence on Use Behavior

The Influence of Behavioral Intention on Use Behavior

Behavioral intention is regarded as the most proximal and strongest predictor of actual use behavior within the UTAUT framework (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Psychologically, intention serves as an internal instruction for an individual to perform a specific action in the future (Loisa & Purwanto, 2020). The greater the commitment and desire of an individual to use a system, the higher the probability that it will manifest in actual usage behavior (Almojaibel et al., 2025). Intention acts as the primary driver that converts mental plans into tangible operational actions (Indah & Agustin, 2019).

H7: Behavioral Intention has a positive influence on Use Behavior

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research employs a quantitative approach with descriptive and verificative methods through an explanatory survey design to test the causal relationships between variables. The primary focus of the study is to confirm the influence of Performance Expectancy, Effort Expectancy, and Social Influence on Behavioral Intention (as a mediating variable) and Use Behavior (as the dependent variable). Data were collected cross-sectionally from Bukalapak users in the Tangerang Raya region, who serve as the unit of analysis. This study is confirmatory in nature, where hypotheses are tested without manipulating the variables, capturing empirical phenomena to be analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM).

The research process encompassed several stages, including preparation, data collection through research instruments, and final result analysis. Given that the population of Bukalapak users in Tangerang Raya is infinite, the sample size was determined using the criteria of Hair et al., by multiplying the number of indicators (60 items) by a minimum constant of 5, resulting in a minimum sample of 300, which was further rounded to 384 respondents to enhance generalization accuracy. The sampling technique utilized was non-probability sampling with a purposive sampling method, targeting respondents aged 18–50 years who had completed at least two purchases in the last month to ensure the validity of the user experience.

Operationally, the research variables are measured using a five-point Likert scale to delineate key dimensions such as perceived usefulness, complexity, subjective norms, and usage loyalty. The research instrument was developed based on the modified

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UTAUT theory, incorporating primary data from structured questionnaires and secondary data from documentation and field observations. All collected data underwent validity, reliability, and normality testing before being subjected to Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) analysis. This process aims to provide a comprehensive conclusion regarding the factors driving technology adoption within e-commerce platforms.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Demographics

Respondent characteristics are described based on gender, age, highest level of education, occupation, domicile, and type of income. Based on the sample determination calculation, the sample size in this study was 384 respondents.

Table 2. Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Category	Description	Frequency	Percent (%)
Gender	Male	163	42.4
	Female	221	57.6
Age	18–25 years	150	39.1
	26–35 years	139	36.2
	36–45 years	46	12.0
	46–50 years	49	12.8
Education Level	Senior High School or equivalent	118	30.7
	Diploma (D3)	64	16.7
	Bachelor's Degree (S1)	168	43.8
	Master's Degree (S2)	34	8.9
Occupation	Student	63	16.4
	Private Employee	123	32.0
	Civil Servant	65	16.9
	Entrepreneur	50	13.0
	Housewife	31	8.1
	Others	52	13.5
Purchase Frequency	2 times	297	77.3
	3–4 times	58	15.1
	More than 4 times	29	7.6
Domicile	Tangerang City	118	30.7
	South Tangerang City	206	53.6
	Tangerang Regency	60	15.6

The respondents consisted of 384 individuals, with a higher proportion of females (57.6%) than males (42.4%). Most respondents were aged between 18–25 years (39.1%) and 26–35 years (36.2%), indicating that the sample was dominated by young adults. In terms of education, the majority held a bachelor's degree (43.8%), followed by senior high school graduates (30.7%). Regarding occupation, private employees represented the largest group (32.0%), followed by civil servants (16.9%) and students (16.4%). Most respondents reported making purchases twice (77.3%), and the majority were domiciled in South Tangerang City (53.6%), reflecting a concentration of respondents in urban areas.

MEASUREMENT MODEL ANALYSIS RESULTS (OUTER MODEL)

Table 3. Outer Model

Item	Loading Factor	T-value	Error	AVE	Cronbach's Alpha
$\{X_{1,\lambda}\}_{11}$	0.987	8.702	0.038	0.953	0.988
$\{X_{1,\lambda}\}_{12}$	0.961	11.705	0.109		
$\{X_{1,\lambda}\}_{13}$	0.969	11.220	0.087		
$\{X_{1,\lambda}\}_{14}$	0.988	8.177	0.034		
$\{X_{2,\lambda}\}_{21}$	0.918	12.784	0.224	0.888	0.955
$\{X_{2,\lambda}\}_{22}$	0.901	12.660	0.250		
$\{X_{2,\lambda}\}_{23}$	1.004	124.939	-0.011		
$\{X_{3,\lambda}\}_{31}$	0.891	10.543	0.215	0.824	0.932
$\{X_{3,\lambda}\}_{32}$	0.955	5.685	0.087		

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Item	Loading Factor	T-value	Error	AVE	Cronbach's Alpha
$\{X_3, \lambda\}_{33}$	0.875	11.034	0.266	0.902	0.756
$\{Y, \lambda\}_{41}$	0.870	9.840	0.361		
$\{Y, \lambda\}_{42}$	0.904	8.087	0.231		
$\{Y, \lambda\}_{43}$	0.834	10.831	0.326	0.903	0.905
$\{Z, \lambda\}_{51}$	0.934	10.553	0.170		
$\{Z, \lambda\}_{52}$	0.960	8.036	0.105		
$\{Z, \lambda\}_{53}$	0.956	8.491	0.117		

Based on the Outer Model results in Table 3, the research instrument demonstrates excellent validity and reliability, meeting all required statistical criteria. All Loading Factors exceed the 0.70 threshold, indicating that each item accurately represents its respective latent variable. The model's robustness is further supported by Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values that all surpass 0.50 (ranging from 0.824 to 0.953), and Cronbach's Alpha values consistently above 0.70, confirming high internal consistency across all constructs. Furthermore, the statistical significance is reinforced by T-values significantly higher than 1.96, concluding that the measurement model is highly valid and reliable for further structural analysis (Inner Model).

STRUCTURAL MODEL ANALYSIS

The resulting structural models were analyzed by observing the correlation coefficient values or figures that emerged from each model. The overall structural diagram obtained in this study is presented as follows.

Figure 2. Structural Model

Based on the structural model diagram, the R-Square value for the Behavioral Intention (Niat Menggunakan) variable is 0.546, indicating that Performance Expectancy, Effort Expectancy, and Social Influence simultaneously explain 54.6% of the variance in user intention. Furthermore, the Use Behavior (Perilaku Penggunaan) variable exhibits a higher R-Square value of 0.644, demonstrating that the model accounts for 64.4% of the variance in actual user behavior through the influence of the independent variables and behavioral intention as a mediator. These values indicate that the model possesses a moderate to strong level of predictive power in explaining technology adoption within the context of this study.

Models in Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) are required to meet Goodness of Fit (GOF) measures. Models obtained through data-model comparisons and that meet these measures can be considered good based on the following criteria.

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Table 4. Model Accuracy Test Criteria

Model Fit Measure	Estimated Model	Cut-Off Value	Result
Chi-square	535.130	Expected to be small	Not Good Fit
P-value	0.000	> 0.05	Not Good Fit
Chi-square/df	5.693	< 2 (good), < 5 (marginal)	Not Good Fit
RMSEA	0.111	< 0.08	Not Good Fit
GFI	0.854	> 0.90	Marginal Fit
AGFI	0.788	> 0.90	Not Good Fit
PGFI	0.590	≥ 0.50	Good Fit
SRMR	0.031	< 0.08	Good Fit
NFI	0.942	> 0.90	Good Fit
TLI	0.938	> 0.90	Good Fit
CFI	0.951	> 0.90	Good Fit

The results of the model fit evaluation indicate that several goodness-of-fit indices have not fully met the recommended thresholds. The chi-square value is relatively high ($\chi^2 = 535.130$) with a significant p-value (0.000), suggesting that the model does not perfectly fit the data. This is further supported by the chi-square/df ratio of 5.693 and the RMSEA value of 0.111, both of which exceed acceptable cut-off values, indicating a lack of overall model fit. However, some incremental and parsimonious fit indices demonstrate acceptable performance, including PGFI (0.590), SRMR (0.031), NFI (0.942), TLI (0.938), and CFI (0.951), which all meet or exceed their respective thresholds. Although GFI shows a marginal fit (0.854) and AGFI does not meet the recommended criterion (0.788), the presence of several good-fit indices suggests that the model has an adequate level of fit and can be considered acceptable for further analysis, despite some limitations in absolute fit measures.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING

Table 5. Hypothesis Testing Results

Structural Path	Path Coefficient	T-Statistic	P-Value	Conclusion
Performance Expectancy → Behavioral Intention	0.272	4.553	0.000	H0 rejected; Performance Expectancy has a significant effect on Behavioral Intention
Effort Expectancy → Behavioral Intention	0.265	4.410	0.000	H0 rejected; Effort Expectancy has a significant effect on Behavioral Intention
Social Influence → Behavioral Intention	0.318	3.284	0.001	H0 rejected; Social Influence has a significant effect on Behavioral Intention
Performance Expectancy → Use Behavior	0.197	4.079	0.000	H0 rejected; Performance Expectancy has a significant effect on Use Behavior
Effort Expectancy → Use Behavior	0.094	2.228	0.026	H0 rejected; Effort Expectancy has a significant effect on Use Behavior
Social Influence → Use Behavior	0.292	4.536	0.000	H0 rejected; Social Influence has a significant effect on Use Behavior
Behavioral Intention → Use Behavior	0.377	5.228	0.000	H0 rejected; Behavioral Intention has a significant effect on Use Behavior

The results of the partial hypothesis testing indicate that all proposed structural relationships are statistically significant. Performance expectancy, effort expectancy, and social influence each have a positive and significant effect on behavioral intention, as reflected by their path coefficients and t-statistics exceeding the critical value with p-values below 0.05. Performance expectancy, effort expectancy, and social influence also significantly influence use behavior, indicating that both individual perceptions and social factors directly affect actual system usage. Furthermore, behavioral intention shows the strongest effect on use behavior, suggesting that users' intention plays a crucial mediating role in translating expectations and social influence into actual usage behavior. Overall, these findings support the proposed model and confirm that the examined constructs are important determinants of behavioral intention and use behavior.

DISCUSSION

The Influence of Performance Expectancy on Behavioral Intention

The findings demonstrate that performance expectancy has a positive and significant effect on behavioral intention. This result indicates that users are more likely to intend to use a technology when they believe it will enhance their performance or provide

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tangible benefits. This finding is consistent with the core proposition of the UTAUT model proposed by Venkatesh et al. (2003), which identifies performance expectancy as the strongest predictor of behavioral intention. Empirical support for this relationship has been reported in various contexts, such as social media adoption among SMEs (Abdat, 2020), mobile payment systems (Gupta & Arora, 2020), e-commerce platforms (Indah & Agustin, 2019), and digital payment services (Paramita & Cahyadi, 2024). Therefore, the result confirms that perceived usefulness remains a critical driver of users' intention to adopt and continue using technology.

The Influence of Effort Expectancy on Behavioral Intention

The results reveal that effort expectancy significantly influences behavioral intention, suggesting that ease of use plays an important role in shaping users' willingness to adopt technology. When a system is perceived as easy to learn and operate, users tend to develop a stronger intention to use it. This finding aligns with previous UTAUT-based studies, which consistently show that lower perceived effort increases adoption intention, particularly in digital platforms and mobile applications (Al-Mamary, 2022; Azizah et al., 2024). Similar results were also reported in studies on e-wallet adoption (Phan et al., 2020) and online learning platforms (Sangeeta & Tandon, 2021). Thus, the present result reinforces the importance of system simplicity in encouraging initial and continued usage.

The Influence of Social Influence on Behavioral Intention

The analysis indicates that social influence has a positive and significant effect on behavioral intention. This suggests that recommendations, opinions, and social pressure from peers, family members, or important others can strongly shape users' intention to use technology. This finding supports the UTAUT framework, which emphasizes the role of social norms in technology acceptance, especially in collectivist cultures (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Prior studies have reported similar results in the contexts of mobile banking (Loisa & Purwanto, 2020), e-commerce adoption (Kartikasari et al., 2021), and digital payment systems (Gunawan, 2019). Consequently, social influence remains a crucial determinant of behavioral intention, particularly in environments where social endorsement plays a significant role in decision-making.

The Influence of Performance Expectancy on Use Behavior

The results show that performance expectancy has a significant direct effect on use behavior, indicating that perceived performance benefits not only influence intention but also directly encourage actual usage. This finding suggests that users who perceive clear advantages from using the technology are more likely to integrate it into their daily activities. Similar findings have been observed in studies on mobile banking adoption (Abu-Taieh et al., 2022), m-health applications (Alam et al., 2021), and e-commerce platforms (Maheswari & Meiranto, 2024). This result confirms that perceived usefulness plays a dual role by influencing both intention and actual behavior, as suggested in extended UTAUT research.

The Influence of Effort Expectancy on Use Behavior

The findings indicate that effort expectancy has a significant effect on use behavior, although its influence is relatively weaker compared to other predictors. This implies that ease of use still contributes to actual technology usage, especially after users have formed an intention. Previous studies also found that effort expectancy influences continued usage behavior in digital payment systems and learning platforms (Ilhamsyah & Purnamasari, 2021; Al-Mamary, 2022). This result suggests that even after adoption, system usability remains important in sustaining long-term use and preventing user resistance.

The Influence of Social Influence on Use Behavior

The results demonstrate that social influence significantly affects use behavior, indicating that social encouragement not only shapes intention but also directly motivates actual usage. This finding is consistent with studies on social commerce adoption (Sarker et al., 2025), mobile health acceptance (Cao et al., 2022), and QR-code payment systems (Suo et al., 2021). The result highlights that social validation and peer usage can strengthen users' confidence and reduce uncertainty, ultimately leading to higher levels of actual use.

The Influence of Behavioral Intention on Use Behavior

The findings confirm that behavioral intention has a strong and significant effect on use behavior, indicating that intention serves as a key predictor of actual technology usage. This result is fully aligned with the fundamental assumption of UTAUT and other technology acceptance theories, which posit that intention is the most immediate antecedent of behavior (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Empirical evidence from various domains, including e-wallet adoption (Damayanti et al., 2021), digital banking (Sharma et al., 2020), and e-commerce platforms (Putri & Yusuf, 2019), supports this relationship. Therefore, strengthening users' behavioral intention is essential for ensuring sustained and effective technology use).

V. CONCLUSION

This study examines behavioral intention and use behavior toward Bukalapak as a digital commerce platform by applying the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). The findings indicate that performance expectancy, effort

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expectancy, and social influence have positive and significant effects on users' behavioral intention to use Bukalapak. Furthermore, performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and behavioral intention significantly influence actual use behavior. Among these relationships, behavioral intention demonstrates the strongest effect on use behavior, confirming its central role as a key predictor of actual technology usage.

The synthesis of findings shows that the research objectives have been fully achieved, as all proposed hypotheses are supported. The results are consistent with the theoretical assumptions of the UTAUT model and reinforce its ability to explain digital technology adoption and usage related to Bukalapak. The significant relationships among expectancy factors, social influence, behavioral intention, and use behavior indicate that users' decisions to use Bukalapak are shaped by perceived performance benefits, ease of use, and social encouragement.

This study provides both theoretical and practical contributions. From a theoretical perspective, the findings strengthen empirical evidence for the applicability of the UTAUT model in explaining user acceptance and usage of e-commerce platforms in Indonesia, particularly Bukalapak. From a practical perspective, the results offer important insights for Bukalapak's management and digital platform developers to enhance user adoption and sustained usage by improving system performance, simplifying user interaction, and leveraging social influence through recommendations and peer-driven promotion strategies.

Despite its contributions, this study has several limitations. The use of cross-sectional data limits the ability to observe changes in user behavior over time. In addition, the model does not incorporate moderating variables such as age, gender, or user experience, which may influence the strength of the examined relationships. Future studies are therefore encouraged to adopt longitudinal designs, include relevant moderating variables, and conduct comparative analyses with other e-commerce platforms to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of digital technology adoption.

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